

TOURISM SITES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The aim of this article is the exploration of tourism development in Uzbekistan, acknowledging its potential for both international and domestic growth. The article also delves into the theoretical and practical aspects of the regions of the country's tourism potential the development of recreational and medical tourism across various areas of the country. Additionally, adventure and gastronomic tourism resources are also mentioned.*

Key words: *Historical sites, winter recreation, Eco-tourism, unique nature, gastronomy tourism.*

Аннотация: *Целью данной статьи является изучение развития туризма в Узбекистане, признание его потенциала как для международного, так и для внутреннего роста. В статье также рассматриваются теоретические и практические аспекты регионов туристического потенциала страны, развитие рекреационного и медицинского туризма в различных областях страны. Кроме того, упоминаются ресурсы приключенческого и гастрономического туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *Исторические места, зимний отдых, экотуризм, уникальная природа, гастрономический туризм.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi O'zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirish, uning xalqaro va ichki o'sish imkoniyatlarini e'tirof etishdan iborat. Maqolada, shuningdek, mamlakatning turizm salohiyati mintaqalarining nazariy va amaliy jihatlari, mamlakatning turli hududlarida rekreatsion va davolash turizmini rivojlantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, sarguzasht va gastronomik turizm resurslari ham qayd etilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tarixiy joylar, qishki dam olish, ekoturizm, betakror tabiat, gastronomiya turizmi.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, tourism is one of the most financially rewarding business. According to Official Website of the International Trade Administration, “Uzbekistan’s exports of tourism services reached \$1.6 billion in 2022 and its targets for 2024 are 7 million foreign tourists and \$2.5 billion in tourism exports”. Obviously, it has become fast growing industry in many parts of the world and Uzbekistan is also in this kind of sphere as it is considered one of the centers of tourism not only in Central Asia, but also across the globe. The government in Uzbekistan also intends to develop tourism because it is one of the best ways to improve regions and their infrastructure. Why one should try travelling to Uzbekistan? The reasons are straightforward! Firstly, visiting Uzbekistan is cost-effective. Secondly, it offers a secure environment. And thirdly, there are abundant activities to engage in while exploring. Uzbekistan is well-known for its unique historical monuments but, a lot of recreational sites such as sanatorium-resort resources, mineral waters, national parks and the cave mountain have significant place in the growth of tourism. It means,

tourists can come to Uzbekistan not only to view ancient architectural monuments and take pleasure in unique nature and culture, but also strengthen their health as the main value of life.

Historical sites and Pilgrimage Visits

A significant milestone in the history of tourism in Uzbekistan was the access of the country in 1993 in the UN World Tourism Organization. Additionally, in 20.08.1999, the Law No. 831-I “On Tourism” was declared by the Decree of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The aim of the Law is developing tourism and protection of the rights of tourists. In 2017, after Shavkat Mirziyoyev became the president of Uzbekistan, tourism was named one of the primary directions of the national economy. Now tourism is most focused direction to develop in Uzbekistan as it is well-known with its historical sites. Undoubtedly, the tourist and recreational potential that Uzbekistan has are huge. According to Aymetova, “there are more than 7,400 cultural heritage sites, more than 200 of which are located in four city-museums - Khiva, Bukhara, Shakhrisabz and Samarkand” (2021) - the cities which are almost as the same age as Rome and Babylon which were one of the biggest and most developed cities of their era. All of them are included in the list of UNESCO world heritage sites. In addition, “the country has 8 nature reserves, 2 natural and 1 national park, 6 natural monuments, 11 nature reserves, more than 50 water protection zones, which are also attractive tourist sites” (Khamidova & Sayfullayev 2020).

Nowadays, all cities of Uzbekistan have the potential of unique tourist resources. Located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, Samarkand region is one of the most attractive tourist centers in the country. It has been attracting visitors with its historical monuments, sacred sites, architectural, unusual traditions of locals and national crafts for so many years. In Bekhnazarov’s article “Opportunities for the use of Tourism resources in Samarkand region in the development of individual types of Tourism” he states that “according to the Main Department for Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage, there are 291 architectural, 1452 archeological, 36 historical, 188 monumental art and sculptural monuments in the region” (2022). Architectural monuments such as Registan Ensemble, Ulugbek, Observatory, Hazrati Hizr Mosque, Ruhobod, Abdi Darun Mausoleum, Shahi Zinda Complex, Gori Amir Mausoleum, Bibikhanim Mosque amaze foreign tourists. According to Bekhnazarov, “During the centuries-old history of Samarkand, culture, art, science, trade and handicrafts have developed. For this reason, many buildings and structures have been built in Samarkand. Especially during the reign of the great master Amir Temur, the city of Samarkand became more beautiful. This has increased the potential of historical and architectural monuments of the region” (2022). In the past few years, a huge number of religious and pilgrimage, historical monuments, mosques and madrasas were reconstructed and repaired. Therefore the number of touristic sites has grown and their state has notably improved. It is significant contribution to the sustainable development of pilgrimage tourism.

Medical Care and Eco-touristic Visits

Uzbekistan can offer not only excursions to historical monuments of architecture, but also quality medical care and good rest. As a result, recreational tourism can also be improved in Uzbekistan as the nature of the country is extremely diverse, so it is difficult to overestimate the role of nature reserves, natural parks, sanctuaries, nurseries in the preservation of the flora and fauna of the country. It means, Uzbekistan is renowned for its health benefits as a travel destination, thanks to its distinctive natural environment and climate. The country has gained a reputation as a leading health resort in Central Asia, with numerous health resorts and recreational facilities located in every region. The majority of these health resorts in Uzbekistan are situated in rural and foothill areas, which contribute positively to the healing and treatment of patients. To

show an example, according to bookatour.me website, “having the abundance of coniferous forests, Zomin in Jizzakh region is excellent place to go for both year-round treatment and prevention, and for winter recreation”. Not without reason it is frequently called the “Uzbek Switzerland” as it welcomes both domestic and international tourists. The favorite place to stay for tourists is Zomin Health Resort. The nice climate and clean air of Zomin are good for treatment of respiratory diseases and nervous system. The sanatorium has everything necessary for qualitative diagnosis and treatment of patients”. According to the [uzbekistan.travel](#) website, Uzbek folk medicine, which is rooted in the teachings of Avicenna, remains prevalent in modern times despite its ancient origins. Some of the most commonly sought-after treatments include acupuncture, leech therapy, cupping acupuncture, mud therapy, hydrotherapy, climatotherapy, and a range of spa treatments. As a result, [akusherstvo.uz](#) website states that “according to official statistics, from January to November 2022, 65.6 thousand foreign people arrived in Uzbekistan for the purpose of treatment”.

For those who are in search of an exhilarating vacation, Uzbekistan offers countless thrilling opportunities for adventure. As [Uzbek Travel](#) website states “another place for those who want to experience of rock climbing, hiking and mountaineering Chimgan Highlands caters many opportunities. Chimgan Highlands have been a host for many other outdoor activities such as hang gliding, skiing, snowboarding and horseback riding. The mountains here are not quite as extreme or scenic as the higher peaks around Almaty and Bishkek, but certain activities (heli-skiing, trekking and rafting come to mind) are more accessible and at least as challenging”. Another places that offer unforgettable experiences are Kyzylkum Desert and Aydarkul Lake. According to the [Nuratatours](#) website, “the desert and lake tour to Kyzylkum Desert and Aydarkul Lake includes activities like desert walking, swimming at the lake, a drive through the scenic steppe, walking and bird-watching in the wetlands”. Another website like [caravanistan.com](#) states, “in the camps, you can stay in a yurt, do a camel trek, or do birdwatching on Aidarkul. On the way, you can visit the town of Nurata, which harbours a few sights, and nearer to Navoi, you can visit the petroglyphs at Sarmysh, one of the biggest petroglyph sites in Central Asia. Staying in a yurt or doing a camel trek is a memorable experience”.

Gastronomic Visits

Uzbekistan's gastronomy is another irresistible aspect of the country that will captivate anyone. While you may be tempted to skip out on sightseeing, the incredible cuisine will entice you to indulge. This is evident even as soon as you step foot in the airport, where the enticing aroma of delectable dishes fills the air. Exploring the culinary wonders of Uzbekistan will provide a taste sensation that will linger with you throughout the year, leaving you eager to recreate the experience in your own kitchen. If you are looking to experience a wide range of flavors and vibrant dishes, Uzbek cuisine is one of the most varied and lively in the entire globe. Uzbekistan's cuisine is known for its incredible richness in the Eastern region. Its strategic location along the Great Silk Road has allowed Uzbekistan to absorb a diverse range of extraordinary dishes from different cultures and tribes, exchanging secrets and recipes. This fusion has transformed dishes from other cultures into national treasures. Every dish in Uzbek cuisine has its own unique characteristics and techniques. One particularly popular and widely-consumed dish among the Uzbek people is pilaf. Plov or pilaf is a key dish in Uzbek cuisine, enjoyed by families of various cultural backgrounds in Uzbekistan. It symbolizes the Uzbek food culture and is a staple in the Uzbek mentality. Typically, plov is traditionally cooked by men in Uzbek culture. As [Uzbekistan.travel](#) website states “It is believed that a guest who has visited Uzbekistan and has not

tasted real Uzbek pilaf, did not know the essence of Uzbek culture and hospitality. Uzbek pilaf is a dish of true gourmets and connoisseurs of Oriental cuisine. There are more than 100 pilaf recipes in the world, and Uzbekistan boasts of its own branded versions.” However, the array of national Uzbek dishes goes far beyond pilaf. By promoting gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan, the country can attract a significant number of tourists from all corners of the globe. Delicious foods like fragrant pilaf, lagman, manti, cooked lamb, and tandoor-kebab are just a few examples of enticing dishes that ignite the senses and stimulate the appetite. According to the Uzbekistan Travel website “in 2018, according to the results of the annual National Geographic Traveler Awards in Russia, Uzbekistan took the first place in the category "Gastronomic tourism". The number of votes for our country was 34%, ahead of Italy (21%) and Azerbaijan(17%)”.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that Uzbekistan is one of the leading countries in Central Asia in terms of tourism development opportunities, and the Republic is rich in historical, archeological, religious, architectural, artistic, recreational and other tourist resources that provide domestic and international flow of tourists. Using the available opportunities will lead to the incredible development of this industry as tourism is a primary focus of Uzbekistan’s government. Moreover, cities such as Samarkand provide great opportunities to develop pilgrimage tourism. In addition to historical tourism, places like Zaamin, Chimgan Highland, Kyzylkum Desert and Aydarkul Lake can contribute a lot to the development of medical and recreational tourism. Also, if you are a foodie and want to To savor the most delectable pilaf, mouthwatering lamb cooked over charcoal, traditional tandoor-kebab, spicy lagman, or crunchy samsa, one should definitely consider visiting Uzbekistan.

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